

Thermal Energy Storage an Overview of One Advanced System Based on the European TESSe2b Project

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ABSTRACT

This article gives an overview of the main results of the H2020 project, TESSe2b. The main objective of the project is to design, develop and demonstrate a modular and low cost system of thermal storage technology based on solar collectors and efficient heat pumps for heating, cooling and hot water production (DHW) contributing to the increase the share of renewables and to the flexibility of the electricity grid. The TESSe2b system consists of a set of thermal energy storage tanks based on phase change materials (PCM). Storage tanks with heat exchangers immersed in PCM were developed for heating, cooling and DWH.

Through CFD simulations and laboratory tests, the best geometries and the most appropriate PCMs were selected, which ensure an adequate heat transfer rate and a quantity of stored energy that guarantees the optimal utilization of the solar thermal energy for heating and DHW preparation, as well as the production of cooling by geothermal heat pumps, with maximum energy efficiency and reduced operating costs. In order to increase the efficiency of geothermal heat pumps, PCMs were also introduced in boreholes heat exchangers.

The solution is being demonstrated in three demo sites (Austria, Cyprus and Spain), where the solution is being validated and its energy performance assessed.

Preliminary results show that the solution works quite well and that the objectives proposed at the beginning of the project will be achieved.

INTRODUCTION

The energy use in buildings has been estimated to be approximately 40% of EU total energy consumption (European Commission, 2019). The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) requires that all new buildings will have nearly zero-energy by the end of 2020, indicating that the low amount of energy that these buildings will require comes mostly from renewable energy sources (RES) (European Commission, 2010). In addition, RES adoption is crucial if Europe is to achieve ambitious energy and emission reduction targets. However, even though this need has been already identified,

the uptake of RES in buildings for domestic heating and hot water is still very limited with a proportion under 1%. Due to this fact, there is a compelling need of encouraging energy efficiency in buildings, enhance green technologies and promote advance thermal energy storage solutions with the view to reduce radically energy consumption and minimize CO₂ emissions.

Energy storage not only reduces the mismatch between supply and demand but also improves the performance and reliability of energy systems and plays an important role in conserving the energy (Dincer and Rosen, 2011; Monodraught Ltd, 2011). It leads to saving premium fuels and makes the system more cost effective by reducing the wastage of energy and capital cost. For example, storage would improve the performance of a power generation plant by load levelling and higher efficiency would lead to energy conservation and lesser generation cost.

There are three types of Thermal Energy Storage (TES) process; sensible heat storage, thermochemical storage and latent heat storage (Baylin, 1979). Sensible heat storage is the most developed technology and there is a variety of low-cost materials available, however it has the lowest storage capacity that significantly increases the system size. Thermochemical storage has the highest storage capacity, but the problems of complicated reactors needed for specific chemical reactions, weak long-term durability (reversibility) and chemical stability restricts its application (Ding and Riffat, 2012).

One of the most efficient methods to store thermal energy is Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage (LHTES). LHTES process can be very attractive due to the advantages of (i) high energy storage density and (ii) integration of PCM that sustain the temperature almost constant during the phase change (Abhat, 1983).

Several materials can be used as PCMs. A common way to distinguish PCMs is by dividing them into organic, inorganic and eutectic PCMs (Rathod and Banerjee, 2013). Organic phase change materials are in general chemically stable, melt and freeze repeatedly without phase segregation and consequent degradation of their latent heat of fusion, self-nucleation means they crystallize do not suffer from super cooling, are non-corrosive, are non-toxic and have a high latent heat of fusion. Inorganic PCMs in general have a rather high heat of fusion, good thermal conductivity, are cheap and non-flammable. However, most of them are corrosive to most metals, undergo super cooling and undergo phase decomposition. Most common inorganic PCMs are hydrated salts (Farid *et al.*, 2004). A problem that has been addressed throughout the available literature is the low thermal conductivity for many promising PCMs (around 0.15–0.2 (W/m.K) for organic PCMs and around 0.5 W/(m K) for inorganic salts). Low thermal conductivity reduces the rate of heat absorption or heat release throughout the PCM, i.e. reducing the effectiveness at which it can store and release thermal energy. This may lead to a system which does not fully utilize the full latent heat storage of PCM materials. Recently, graphite based PCM systems and metal foams have been getting increased attention. One solution that has been investigated includes adding of a material with a high thermal conductivity to the PCM. A material that has been investigated for this purpose is various carbon-based nano-fillers. Though the results are varying, the increase in thermal conductivity has increased between 65 and 336% in such studies (Babaei *et al.*, 2013; Evola *et al.*, 2013; Fan and Khodadadi, 2011; Ji *et al.*, 2012).

TESSe2b project will enable the optimal use of renewable energy and provide one of the most advantageous solutions for correcting the mismatch that often occurs between the supply and demand of energy in residential buildings. The target of TESSe2b is to design, develop, validate and demonstrate a modular and low cost thermal storage technology based on solar collectors and highly efficient heat pumps for heating, cooling and domestic hot water (DHW) production.

The idea is to develop advanced compact integrated PCM TES tanks exploiting RES (solar and geothermal) in an efficient manner coupled with enhanced PCM Borehole Heat Exchangers (BHEs) that will take advantage of the increased underground thermal storage and maximize the efficiency of the ground coupled heat pumps (GCHP), and be controlled by smart model-based control system. The TES tanks developed within TESSe2b project will be integrated with different PCM materials; paraffins and salt-hydrates, while in both of them a highly efficient heat exchanger will be included. Even if the concept of phase change thermal stores has been demonstrated, TESSe2b project discriminates itself through incorporating: PCM materials innovation; advanced energy management; enhanced PCM BHEs and compact modular design of thermal storage tank. In the last year of the project, the TESSe2b system has been demonstrated and validated on a real scale in three houses, Austria, Cyprus and Spain, with the objective of covering

different climate conditions.

The TESse2b project is a European project, funded at € 4.3 million under the Horizon 2020 program, which began in October 2015 and lasts 4 years. The consortium consists of five higher education institutions, one research centre and three SME and a non-profit organization, from 8 countries, Portugal, Greece, Cyprus, Spain, Austria, Germany and the United Kingdom.

DESCRIPTION OF OVERALL SYSTEM

The TESse2b solution integrates compact TES PCM Tanks with solar collectors and highly efficient geothermal heat pumps with PCM enhanced BHEs. To optimize the energetic and economic performance of the entire system, TESse2b solution is managed by an advanced energy smart self-learning control system specially developed for this application.

TESse2b solution has TES tanks that store energy at three different levels, according to the specific application. The cold storage tanks for residential space cooling, the hot storage tanks for residential space heating and a TES tank that operate at a high temperature to produce DHW. The system layout (Figure 1) exemplifies the general structure of the TESse2b solution implemented in the Spanish demo site, with the solar collectors, one DHW tank (DHW_PCM), four Hot TES tanks (HTES), two Cold TES tanks (CTES) and the geothermal heat pump with PCM enhanced BHEs. Each demo site has a customized solution for its specific needs, as will all the buildings fitted with the the TESse2b solution.

Figure 1 TESse2b system layout (Spanish demo site)

PCM tanks

Solutions of tanks and their immersed exchangers were studied for two types of PCMs, paraffins and hydrated salts. For both types of PCMs the most suitable solutions for each type of tank (HTES, CTES and DHW_PCM) were selected. In Table 1 it is showed the selected PCMs.

Table 1. Phase Change Materials for HTES, CTES & DHW

PCM*	Phase Change Temp. (°C)	Application	Type
Paraffin 44	44	HTES	Naturally derived blend of alkanes
Paraffin 9	9	CTES	Naturally derived blend of alkanes
Paraffin 53	53	DHW_PCM	Refined paraffin wax blend
Hydrated Salt 44	44	HTES	Salt hydrate with nucleating agents.
Hydrated Salt 10	10	CTES	Salt hydrate with salt-based freeze point depressants and nucleating agents.
Hydrated Salt 58	58	DHW_PCM	Salt hydrate.

The TESse2b tanks were designed in a compact and modular manner for an easy integration into the buildings. The tanks design was done according to the European standards and supported by computational Finite Element Analysis (FEA).

Two tank geometries were designed due to the limitations of hydrated salts. Due to the phase separation effect taking place in salt hydrates over the melting/solidification process it was defined that the height of the Heat Exchanger (HE), for salt hydrates application should not exceed 50 mm to minimize the phase separation issue. For that case, it was necessary to use multiple tanks interconnecting to increase volume (height than area). Figure 2 shows one of this tank during the test phase in a laboratory.

A second problem that it was necessary to solve was the corrosion issue related with the HE metals that are in contact with salt hydrates. It was found that AlN is an effective and thin protective coating against corrosive salt hydrates, whit no negative impact in the heat transfer conditions.

Figure 2 PCM tanks, salt hydrates (HTES, CTESs and DHW_PCM)

For the paraffins the final design consists in a polypropylene tank reinforced by five horizontal ribs and three steel bars (Figure 3). Inside each tank, there are high performance tubes and fins HE designed to achieve the required heat transfer rate between the PCM and the heat carrier fluid during the TES tanks operation (charge/discharge process). The HE design was supported by CFD simulations (ANSYS/Fluent software) and laboratorial experimental tests. The modular design of the tanks allows easily fit the total energy storage capacity of the system to each building, selecting the appropriate

number of tanks. The internal volume of each tank is approximately 180 L (PCM plus HE).

As far as the material is concerned for the tanks polypropylene (PP) was selected as the best option. PP is affected after being in warm contact with the organic PCM tested. For that purpose, an epoxy-based product was tested as a possible protective coating. No effect occurred on the hardness properties and mass uptake of samples using epoxy-based product coating (Chalkia *et al.*, 2018).

In order to increase the thermal performance the paraffins, nano-platelets of expanded graphite mixed in paraffin were found to increase the thermal conductivity at relative low weight concentration. It was demonstrated that for the PCM Paraffin 53, a 1% and 6% weight fraction of adequate shape, 15 μ m in diameter and 6-8nm thick graphite nano-particles, increased the thermal conductivity by 100% to 250% respectively. At the same time the heat of fusion was only slightly reduced from 2-10% for the 1% and 6% weight fractions respectively. It was also demonstrated that, upon addition of graphite nano-platelets in other paraffins, the general trend is similar and therefore it could be useable for the many applications. However, it was found that for the optimized HE geometry developed in the present project the thermal conductivity of the PCMs is important, although not the critical thermal property. Thus it was decided to use the paraffins without the addition of nanoparticles.

Figure 3 PCM tanks, paraffins (HTES, CTESs and DHW_PCM)

PCM Enhanced BHEs for Ground Source Heat Pump

Another innovation of TESSe2b project is the development of a BHE that can also be used for the storage of thermal energy, thus supporting the system in order to increase its performance in the heating and cooling mode. During the operation of the heat pump in the heating mode, the temperature of the heat carrier fluid within the BHE will decrease, and during the cooling it will increase. As the heat transfer in the ground is mainly conductive and its thermal diffusivity is low, this leads to a much slower ground thermal response than the heat pump requirements, resulting in thermal waves being transmitted into the ground, which penalize the performance of GSHP systems. Adding PCMs into the boreholes is regarded as an effective mean to store thermal energy in the BHEs and improves the performance of GSHP systems. The thermal energy stored into the PCMs will smooth the ground thermal wave generated by the GSHP operation and enhance the SPF (seasonal performance factor) of the system. Depending on the PCM phase change temperature this can be applied to the heating or cooling mode.

Figure 4 shows the effect of the PCMs on the BHEs, based in numerical simulations where it is possible to observe, in the heating mode, a smoothing of the fluid temperature during the heating peak load periods.

Figure 4 Expected impact of the implementation of PCMs into the boreholes over the heating season (green line)

The PCMs used in the BHE are paraffins and the selected phase change temperature took into account the ground temperature at each location of the demo sites and the most critical mode of operation, heating or cooling. For Austria and Spain the most critical mode is the heating mode and the phase change temperature considered was 9 °C for Austria (Paraffin 9) and 12 °C for Spain (Paraffin 12). For Cyprus the critical mode is the cooling and the phase change temperature considered was 28 °C (Paraffin 28).

Smart Control System

To optimize the entire system, due to its complexity, it was developed a self-learning management system that will use an algorithm combining a prototype model, a user profile database, weather forecasting and multi-variable controls. This adapts the system operation to the building user schedule and with weather forecasting to take maximum advantage of available energy that is or is going to be stored while taking advantage of lower energy tariffs during night time. The control system will be managed based on the input of an array of sensors and actuators that will automatically change the system mode of operation according to the needs of the building.

DEMO SITES

Aiming to evaluate the system's integration into building space, a demonstration and on-site monitoring evaluation of TESse2b solution is being held in three pilot sites (Austria, Cyprus and Spain) to assess its impact in different climate conditions, and provide evidence about its overall technical and economic feasibility. Table 2 show the characteristics of each demo site. To design the installation it was used a building energy simulation software, Design Builder. The values in the table represent the real installation except the heating and cooling needs that are based in the simulation results.

Figure 5 shows the pictures of the demo sites, corresponding to the three single family houses.

Table 2. Demo site characteristics

DEMOSITE	AUSTRIA	CYPRUS	SPAIN
AREA (m ²)	321	221	138
Heating capacity (kW)	13.0	26.3	12.2
Cooling capacity (kW)	(free-cooling)	18.6	12.6
Heating annual needs (kW/m ²)*	55.1	45.3	63.9
Cooling annual needs (kW/m ²)*	8.67	69.9	6.85
Solar collectors area (m ²)	13.6	23.5	23.5
HTES tanks	4	3	4
CTES tanks	-	3	2
DHW_PCM tank	1	1	1
Borehole he n°	4	8	2+2
Depth (m)	75	90	90
Total Length (m)	300	720	180+180

* Estimated by numerical simulation

Figure 5 Demo sites, single family houses, Austria, Cyprus and Spain, respectively

RESULTS

Since the analysis of demo site monitoring results is still at an early stage, most of the results presented in this section are based on the energy numerical simulation of buildings and their systems. Table 3 shows the preliminary results from numerical simulations for the TESSe2b system in the three demo sites.

Table 3. Demo site results predicted by numerical simulations

DEMOSITE	AUSTRIA	CYPRUS	SPAIN
Solar Fraction Heating (%)	7	30.5	21.8
Solar Fraction Heating + DHW (%)	15.8	42.3	37.1
Heating needs shifted day to night (total - solar) (%)	41.6	44.8	0
Cooling needs shifted day to night (%)	(free-cooling)	30.3	95.3

Table 3 shows that solar heating fractions range from 7% for Austria to 30.5% for Cyprus. The low value for Austria

is due to the low solar radiation on site and also the smallest solar collector area which has been reduced from 23.5 m², of predicted to 13.6 m² due to limited space on the roof. If DHW production is also included, the solar fraction varies between 15.8% for Austria and 42.3% for Cyprus. Another important result is the contribution to the flexibility of the electricity grid and the possibility to take advantage of low electricity tariffs in accordance with existing tariff schemes. The heating needs that can be moved from the day, high electricity tariff, to be produced at night, low electrical tariff correspond to 41.6% for Austria and 44.8% for Cyprus. Due to the specific characteristics of the thermal envelope of the house in Spain and its climate there was no impact on this. Similar effect can be observed for cooling, corresponding at 30.3% for Cyprus and 95.3% for Spain.

After the monitoring process, with the results obtained, these results predicted by simulation can be validated or corrected, as the case may be, obtaining the real performance of the system.

Other important results regarding the performance of PCM tanks are related to the amount of energy stored and the energy transfer rate (heating or cooling capacity). Table 4 shows the main characteristics of the PCM tanks obtained in laboratory tests.

Table 4. Characteristics of the PCM tanks (HTES, CTES and DHW_PCM)

DEMOSITE	AUSTRIA	CYPRUS	SPAIN
AREA (m ²)	321	221	138
Number of HTES tanks	4	3	4
Total energy stored (heating) (kWh)	29.2	21.9	29.2
Average TES capacity (heating) (kW)	18.0	13.5	18.0
Number of CTES tanks	-	3	2
Total energy stored (cooling) (kWh)	-	14.5	9.5
Average TES capacity (cooling) (kW)	-	31.5	21.0
Number of DHW_PCM tanks	1	1	1
Total energy stored (DHW) (kWh)	6.2	6.2	6.2
Supply water temperature (°C)	40-50	40-50	40-50

The number of HTES tanks and consequently the amount of stored energy were selected taking into account the availability of solar radiation, the heating needs and their costs. The CTES tanks and the amount of stored energy were selected were selected taking into account the change in cold production from day to night and the related costs.

The heating capacity for Austria and for Spain is higher than the installed capacity of the respective heat pumps. This means that as long as the PCM tanks have stored energy, they are able to cover all needs even at peak times without any help from the heat pump. For Cyprus the HTES capacity is 13.5 kW while the installed capacity for heating is 26.3 kW (table 2). However the higher heating capacity installed is only due to the needed cooling capacity from the heat pump. The design heating capacity is only 17 kW. Even so, the capacity is superior to the tanks. This means that if the tanks are warming up they may need the heat pump support to cover their needs at some peak hours per year. For cooling it is possible to observe that the CTES are able to cover all cooling needs, in terms of capacity even during the peak hours.

CONCLUSIONS

In the TESSe2b project, a system based on latent thermal energy storage was developed, using two renewable energy sources, solar and geothermal, contributing to the increase of energy efficiency and the share of RES in the heating, cooling and DHW production in residential buildings.

Several technological advances have been made, namely, design a compact modular TES tanks including a high performance HE immersed in PCMs, a new nano-composite enhanced paraffin PCM (NEPCM) with a significant increase of the thermal conductivity, development of a protective thin film coating against the corrosivity of salt-hydrates to the heat exchanger (HE), enhanced PCM borehole heat exchangers and the development of a smart model-based control system.

Numerical simulations and experimental tests performed show promising results. At the moment the System is being validated and demonstrated on three demo sites and it is expected that the monitoring results will soon show the real values of increasing energy efficiency, increasing the share of renewable energy sources, lowering energy tariff and increasing the contribution for the flexibility of the electricity grid.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

TESSe2b project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under the Grant Agreement number 680555. This article reflects only the author’s view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

The project is coordinated by the Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal, Portugal.

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